

Clockwise, from left: a worker at Totilis Camp shows her Obama pride; Kenyan schoolchildren; the writer poses with the Masai

Roots and Rejoicing

In Kenya, a city girl finds a land brimming with wonders and Obama anticipation

By **WILMA ANN ANDERSON**

Visiting the ancestral roots of America's 44th president was a special gift for me—especially since the journey started on my birthday last April. Still seven months from the American general election, Kenya was a nation throbbing with excitement over the prospect of a black president—one with a Kenyan connection, no less. At the mention of Barack Obama's name, the light in their eyes instantly brightened. He gave them hope that America's change would positively affect their land. Kenyan baby boys are being named Obama and Barack in record numbers. There is even a drink named after America's President-elect. How's that for loyalty to kin?

A sign on Uhuru Highway from the airport into Nairobi read "Tujenge Uchumi Yetu!" ("Let's Build Our Nation!") The streets of Nairobi were brimming with a portion of its 3.4 million residents. The city looked much like many other capital cities—bustling commerce, street vendors and hustlers. From the window of the Serena Nairobi hotel (one of a handful of five-star hotels in the city), aerial views of Central Park and downtown Nairobi were breathtaking. This flagship property of Serena Hotel's Fleet of Hotels is designed with Moroccan and African flair and boasts amenities that ensure your every comfort in a far-away land.

Being a 6-foot tall woman, I have always had a special place in my heart for giraffes. Getting to meet one face-

to-face strengthened the lifelong bond I've had with the tallest animal on earth. The Giraffe Centre is a nonprofit organization whose main objective is to provide conservation education for schoolchildren in Kenya. Well, my school days are far behind me, but I sure felt like a big kid when feeding my favorite animals. Watching braver visitors feed the giraffes mouth-to-mouth (by placing a crouton-like morsel on their own tongues and having the giraffes slurp it off their faces) was enough giraffe excitement to last me another lifetime.

Watching the women workers at Kazuri Beads hand make beautiful beaded jewelry from start to finish tickled my arts and crafts fancy. Clay from the Mt. Kenya area is cleaned and shaped and set to dry before the beads are hand painted and made to come alive. *Kazuri* means small and beautiful in Swahili. And for many of the women who were in distressed situations, rescued and empowered through work at Kazuri, the miracle in each bead is a testament to the maxim that great things come in small packages. (www.kazuribeadsusa.com)

I was a small thing in a great big package when I

was sitting in a zippered, mosquito-proof tent in the middle of bush land. *Can anyone hear me if I scream?* I wondered. *Help me.* This lifestyle, living so close to nature, is the Kenyan way. I was getting squeamish about the pet gecko in my tent's bathroom, and monkeys were sleeping in trees just outside. *What was I doing here in the motherland? Why did I insist on connecting with my ancestors?* Just then, I thought I heard a guttural noise. I convinced myself it was nothing, yet vision of rebellious lions defying the electric fence danced in my head. This was my experience in Tortilis Camp in Amboseli National Park. The camp's name comes from the many acacia tortilis trees surrounding it. The rustic environment was a challenge for a scaredy-cat, city slicker like me, but quite a wonderful experience for nature lovers. The open, thatched-roof dining area was awesome, as were the views of Kilimanjaro. Upon leaving, I decided that I was glad I braved the wild. Tortilis was a memorable stop on my journey of "firsts."

Safaris, game drives and imagined midnight encounters with tigers are not all Kenya has to offer, of course, but they definitely provide an exciting

opposite page: a resident of the Giraffe Centre, up close; this page: working with the Kazuri beads

diversion from indoors-y attractions. A game drive through Tsavo West National Park revealed elephants, zebra, dik-dik, and a wounded lioness and two of her cubs near the roadside. Park rangers frequently patrol the park and must have kept her and the cubs alive with daily feedings. An amazing feeling is to be a fly on the wall of nature. This experience was one of my favorite movies ("The Lion King") come to life. I was on the African plains. Wow. Thankfully, I didn't get paralyzed by my awe to the point where I dawdled on the reserve because I had another first to experience at the Salt Lick Lodge.

Salt Lick Lodge was a welcoming place to retreat at the end of a game drive. Situated in Taita Hills Wildlife Sanctuary, adjacent to Tsavo West, the lodge

will absolutely intrigue you. A suspended walkway leads to clutches of cabins on stilts. The rooms come complete with netted beds, which are a big plus as the area might bug you out a little. (Pun intended.) There is an awesome view of one of the watering holes from each room and the lounge area. The fine African cuisine nearly knocked me off my feet. But I kept my balance with a little encouragement from the watering hole visitors.

The Fort Jesus Light Show in Mombasa was riveting. The town was filled with lots of history and the town's Arabic influences can be seen at every turn. There seemed to be a carefree vibe throughout the streets. The people were kind and seemed to be enjoying life. This was the disposition of all of the Kenyans

I encountered—from the man working at the gas station to the local vendors, to the higher-ups at the Kenyatta International Conference Centre.

But the country has taken a hit because of negative media coverage of political rifts and isolated violence. I found Kenya to be a safe place to experience “God’s Green Earth.”

The vendors on the beach must have rejoiced loud and long at the news of Obama’s presidency because they will now see tourist traffic that hasn’t been in full flux since early in the year. I met some of these vendors when visiting the Voyager Hotel. The marine vessel theme at the Voyager was everywhere, but you

soon ignore the maritime puns and just enjoy the swimmable beach replete with camel rides and artists and sculptors waiting to carve your memories into a piece of pure ebony.

I am proud to be an American but happy to have bonded with the motherland and the homeland of my President-elect. Kenya deserves the attention of anyone eager to enjoy a memorable experience carved into a piece of pure ebony—an experience of grace and beauty, even through a little fire.

Wilma Ann Anderson is a New Jersey-based writer and founder of MahoganyBaby.com.